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Research Article

**A STABILITY INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD
DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR SIMULTANEOUS
ESTIMATION OF LORNOXICAM, PARACETAMOL AND
SERRATIOPEPTIDASE IN COMBINED FORMULATION****Dr. Gampa Vijay Kumar^{1,2} M.Bala Vidya Sagar³**^{1,2} Professor and Head, Dept. of Pharmacy, KGR Institute of Technology and Management, Rampally, Kesara, Rangareddy, Telangana, India.³KGR Institute of Technology and Management, Rampally, Kesara, Rangareddy, Telangana, India.**Abstract:**

For routine analytical purpose it is desirable to establish methods capable of analyzing huge number of samples in a short time period with good robustness, accuracy and precision without any prior separation step. HPLC method generates large amount of quality data, which serve as highly powerful and convenient analytical tool. Lornoxicam & Paracetamol was freely soluble in water and alcohol. Serratiopeptidase was freely soluble in alcohol and sparingly soluble in water. Methanol and potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate (pH 3) was chosen as the mobile phase. The run time of the HPLC procedure was 10 minutes. The method was validated for system suitability, linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity, ruggedness robustness, LOD and LOQ. The system suitability parameters were within limit, hence it was concluded that the system was suitable to perform the assay. The method shows linearity between the concentration range of 10-100 µg / ml. The % recovery of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase were found to be in the range of 99.22 % - 100.11 %. As there was no interference due to excipients and mobile phase, the method was found to be specific. The method was robust and rugged as observed from insignificant variation in the results of analysis by changes in Flow rate and Mobile phase composition separately and analysis being performed by different analysts. Good agreement was seen in the assay results of Pharmaceutical formulation by developed method. Hence it can be concluded that the proposed method was a good approach for obtaining reliable results and found to be suitable for the routine analysis of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase in Bulk drug and Pharmaceutical formulation.

Keywords: Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase, HPLC**Corresponding author:**

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INTRODUCTION:

Paracetamol is an analgesic-antipyretic agent. It is effective in treating mild-to-moderate pain such as headache, neuralgia, and pain of musculo-skeletal origin.¹ Owing to widespread use of paracetamol in different kinds of pharmaceutical preparations, rapid and sensitive methods for the determination of paracetamol individual and in combination are being investigated. The most recent methods for determination of paracetamol include chromatographic, [2-5] electrochemical, [6-7] spectrophotometric, [8] and fluorescence spectroscopic techniques. Lornoxicam 6-chloro-4-hydroxy-2-methyl-1,1-dioxo-N-(pyridin-2-yl)-2H-1 λ 6-thieno[2,3-e] [1,2] thiazine-3-carboxamide is a

nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug with analgesic and antipyretic properties that belongs to the class of oxicams. Literature review reveals that there is no analytical method reported for the analysis of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase by simultaneous estimation by RP-HPLC [9] The present work describes the development of a simple, precise, accurate and reproducible spectrophotometric method for the simultaneous estimation of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase in Combined Formulation[10]. The developed method was validated in accordance with ICH Guidelines and successfully employed for the assay of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase in Combined Formulation [11].

MATERIALS AND METHOD AND INSTRUMENTATION:

Ortho phosphoric acid, Acetonitrile, Methanol, Water, KH₂PO₄, K₂HPO₄

HPLC instrument is Shimadzu, model No. SPD-20MA LC+20AD, Software- LC-20 Solution, U.V double beam spectrometer, UV 3000+, U.V win soft ware, Lab India, pH meter, Sonicator, Digital weighing balance(sensitivity 5mg).

Chromatographic conditions

TRIAL-5

Chromatographic conditions (Optimized Method)

Mobile phase	: Methanol: phosphate buffer P ^H 3 (70:30)
Flow rate	: 1 ml per min
Column	: ThermoHypersil BDS, C18,(150 x 4.6 mm,5 μ m)
Detector wavelength	: 260 nm
Column oven	: Ambient
Injection volume	: 10 μ l
Run time	: 10 min
Rt	: 3.494,4.417,8.087.

Fig.No.1 Chromatogram For Optimized Method.

Observation :Thus a method has been optimized where Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase. Both the components were eluted with good retention times & peak shapes.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution

Weigh accurately about 10 mg of Lornoxicam, 10mg of Paracetamol and 20mg of Serratiopeptidase were transferred into 10 ml volumetric flask and about 7 ml of diluent was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely. The volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent to give the concentration of 1000 µg/ml. (Stock solution) .Further 0.3ml was pipette out from the above stock solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 30 µg/ml ,30 µg/ml and 60 µg/ml respectively.

Sample preparation

Weigh 20 tablets and grind to fine powder in a dry mortar. Transfer 200 mg of the equivalent powder into a 100 ml volumetric flask. Add 50 ml of diluent and sonicate for 30 minutes and shake for 30 minutes. Dilute to volume with diluent and mix. Filter through 0.45µm membrane filter by discarding the first 5 ml. Dilute 3 ml of the above solution to 200 ml with the diluent.

METHOD VALIDATION:

1.SYSTEM SUITABILITY:

Sample solution of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase were injected three times into HPLC system as per test procedure. The system suitability parameters were evaluated from standard Chromatograms obtained, by calculating the % RSD of retention times, tailing factor, theoretical plates and peak areas from three replicate injections.

2.LINEARITY:

Preparation of stock solution:

10 mg of Lornoxicam, 10 mg of Paracetamol and 20 mg of Serratiopeptidase were accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, about 7 ml of diluent was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent to give a concentration of 1000 µg/ml. (Stock solution).

3. PRECISION:

10 mg of Lornoxicam, 10 mg of Paracetamol ,20 mg of Serratiopeptidase were accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, about 7 ml of diluent was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely. The volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent to give the

concentration of 1000 µg/ml. (Stock solution)

4. INTERMEDIATE PRECISION/RUGGEDNESS:

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness) of the method Precision was performed on different day by using different make column of same

Dimensions.

5. ACCURACY:

Assay was performed in triplicate for various concentrations of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase equivalent to 50, 100, and 150 % of the standard amount was injected into the HPLC system as per the test procedure.

6. SPECIFICITY:

Solutions of Standard and Sample were prepared as per test procedure and injected into the HPLC system.

7.ROBUSTNESS:

The robustness of the proposed method was determined by analysis of aliquots from homogenous lots by differing physical parameters like flow rate and mobile phase composition, temperature variations which may differ but the responses were still within the specified limits of the assay.

8. LIMIT OF DETECTION:

LOD's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) at levels approximating the LOD according to the formula. The standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

9.LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION (LOQ):

LOQ's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) according to the formula. Again, the standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Wavelength Detection

The detection wavelength was selected by dissolving the drug in mobile phase to get a concentration of 10µg/ml for individual and mixed standards. The resulting solution was scanned in U.V range from 200-400nm. The overlay spectrum of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase was obtained and the isobestic point of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and

Serratiopeptidase showed absorbance's maxima at 260 nm.

Fig.No.2 Overlay spectrum of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase

SYSTEM SUITABILITY:

Lornoxicam

Table No: 1. Chromatogram values for System suitability

Injection	R _t	Peak Area	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	3.568	1250763	2487	1.62
2	3.566	1247867	2489	1.58
3	3.563	1255849	2496	1.64
Mean		1251493		
SD		4040.762		
% RSD		0.322875		

Paracetamol

Table No: 2 Chromatogram values for System suitability

Injection	R _t	Peak Area	USP Plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	4.480	940627	2281	1.51	3.04
2	4.478	931161	2244	1.47	3.09
3	4.477	940306	2261	1.47	3.05
Mean		937364.7			
SD		5374.93			
% RSD		0.573409			

Serratiopeptidase

Table No: 3. Chromatogram values for System suitability

Injection	R _t	Peak Area	USP Plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	8.097	932578	2508	1.25	12.95
2	8.098	934464	2594	1.25	13.23
3	8.097	920416	2567	1.23	13.16
Mean		929152.7			
SD		7624.714			
% RSD		0.820609			

SAMPLE CHROMATOGRAMS:

Lornoxicam

Table No: 4. Chromatogram values for Lornoxicam

Injection	R _t	Peak Area	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	3.559	1248895	2486	1.59
2	3.562	1250689	2488	1.61
Mean		1249792		
SD		1268.55		
% RSD		0.101501		

Paracetamol

Table No: 5. Chromatogram values for Paracetamol

Injection	R _t	Peak Area	USP Plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	4.472	940585	2275	1.52	3.07
2	4.476	941258	2263	1.49	3.02
Mean		940921.5			
SD		475.8829			
% RSD		0.050576			

Serratiopeptidase

Table No: 6. Chromatogram values for Serratiopeptidase

Injection	R _t	Peak Area	USP Plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	8.097	932587	2524	1.28	12.99
2	8.098	945682	2538	1.26	12.87
Mean		939134.5			
SD		9259.53			
% RSD		0.985968			

LINEARITY:**Table No: 7. Linearity results for Lornoxicam**

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	10 ppm	412230
2	II	20 ppm	824568
3	III	30 ppm	1225696
4	IV	40 ppm	1648952
5	V	50 ppm	2063358
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Table No: 8. Linearity results for Paracetamol

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	10 ppm	332851
2	II	20 ppm	635247
3	III	30 ppm	938520
4	IV	40 ppm	1267895
5	V	50 ppm	1585698
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Table.No: 9. Linearity results for Serratiopeptidase

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	20 ppm	298895
2	II	40 ppm	618074
3	III	60 ppm	925612
4	IV	80 ppm	1254149
5	V	100 ppm	1575861
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Lornoxicam $r^2 = 0.999$

Fig.No.3 Calibration curve of Lornoxicam

Paracetamol $r^2 = 0.999$

Fig.No.4 Calibration curve of Paracetamol

Serratiopeptidase $r^2 = 0.999$

Fig.No. 5 Calibration curve of Serratiopeptidase

Table.No: 10. Calibration parameters for Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase

Parameter	Results for Lornoxicam	Results for Paracetamol	Results for Serratiopeptidase
Slope	3031	10539	22893
Intercept	41266	31383	31908
Correlation co-efficient	0.99996	0.99985	0.99995

PRECISION REPEATABILITY:**Table No: 11. Standard Chromatogram values for Repeatability Lornoxicam**

Injection No	Peak Area	R _t
1	1247256	3.365
2	1248579	3.368
3	1243273	3.368
4	1243262	3.367
5	1249574	3.630
Avg	1246389	
SD	2965.62	
% RSD	0.23793	

Table No: 12. Standard Chromatogram values for Repeatability Paracetmol

Injection No	Peak Area	R _t
1	935035	4.595
2	929353	4.573
3	930459	4.573
4	932389	4.573
5	922057	4.569
Avg	929858.6	
SD	4865.16	
% RSD	0.5232	

Table No: 13. Standard Chromatogram values for Repeatability Serratiopeptidase

Injection No	Peak Area	R_t
1	954854	8.097
2	937615	8.092
3	950694	8.092
4	940252	8.075
5	922057	8.090
Avg	941094.4	
SD	12813.25	
% RSD	1.3615	

Sample Chromatograms for Precision**Table No: 14. Sample Chromatogram values for Repeatability Lornoxicam**

Injection No	Peak Area	R_t
1	1257254	3.254
2	1257857	3.562
3	1265874	3.255
4	1258742	3.256
5	1235897	3.251
6	1258978	3.257
Avg	1255768	
SD	10224.57	
% RSD	0.81	

Table No: 15. Sample Chromatogram values for Repeatability Paracetmol

Injection No	Peak Area	R_t
1	935289	4.572
2	958525	4.571
3	954587	4.573
4	941863	4.574
5	935845	4.576
6	945812	4.578
Avg	945320.2	
SD	9621.214	
% RSD	1.02	

Table No: 16. Sample Chromatogram values for Repeatability Serratiopeptidase

Injection No	Peak Area	R_t
1	953258	8.091
2	958754	8.053
3	932547	8.092
4	954215	8.093
5	946857	8.080
6	942657	8.094
Avg	948048	
SD	9492.7	
% RSD	1.00	

INTERMEDIATE PRECISION/RUGGEDNESS:**Standard Chromatograms for intermediate Precision****Table No: 17. Standard Chromatogram values of Lornoxicam for Intermediate precision**

Injection No	Peak Area	R _t
1	1231404	3.561
2	1256357	3.560
3	1231008	3.561
4	1238575	3.566
5	1232407	3.562
Mean	1242320	
SD	11798.77	
% RSD	0.95	

Table No: 18. Standard Chromatogram values of Paracetamol for Intermediate precision

Injection No	Peak Area	R _t
1	946589	4.472
2	935814	4.476
3	945821	4.472
4	948458	4.473
5	954875	4.473
Mean	946311.4	
SD	6863.96	
% RSD	0.73	

Table No: 19. Standard Chromatogram values of Serratiopeptidase for Intermediate precision

Injection No	Peak Area	R _t
1	934589	8.099
2	948975	8.098
3	955895	8.095
4	935489	8.096
5	945875	8.098
Mean	944164.6	
SD	9091.56	
% RSD	0.96	

Sample Chromatograms for intermediate Precision :**Table.No: 20. Sample Chromatogram values for Intermediate precision Lornoxicam**

Injection No	Peak Area	R _t
1	1235897	3.562
2	1245895	3.563
3	1248524	3.569
4	1245784	3.567
5	1251458	3.566
6	1235842	3.568
Avg	1243900	
SD	9091.56	
% RSD	0.96	

Table.No: 21. Sample Chromatogram values for Intermediate precision Paracetmol

Injection No	Peak Area	R_t
1	934895	4.476
2	945879	4.477
3	935487	4.481
4	929541	4.479
5	945781	4.478
6	958457	4.480
Avg	94673.3	
SD	10465.77	
% RSD	1.11	

Table.No: 22. Sample Chromatogram values for Repeatability Serratiopeptidase

Injection No	Peak Area	R_t
1	954125	8.092
2	937898	8.097
3	945812	8.099
4	943587	8.096
5	951489	8.098
6	954875	8.097
Avg	947964.3	
SD	6682.201	
% RSD	0.70	

ACCURACY:**Table .No.: 23. Chromatogram Values For Accuracy of Lornoxicam.**

Sample No.	Accuracy Levels	Amount added(mg)	Amount found(mg)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
1	50 %	5	4.9	98%	100%
		5	5.1	102%	
		5	5	100%	
2	100 %	10	9.88	98.8%	99.13%
		10	9.91	99.1%	
		10	9.95	99.5%	
3	150 %	15	14.89	99.2%	99.33%
		15	14.86	99.0%	
		15	14.99	99.79%	

Table.No:24.Chromatogram Values For Accuracy of Paracetamol

Sample No.	Accuracy Levels	Amount added(mg)	Amount found(mg)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
1	50 %	5	4.9	98%	100%
		5	5.1	102%	
		5	5	100%	
2	100 %	10	9.98	99.8%	99.46%
		10	9.91	99.1%	
		10	9.95	99.5%	
3	150 %	15	14.89	99.2%	99.51%
		15	14.86	99.6%	
		15	14.82	99.74%	

Table.No: 25.Chromatogram Values For Accuracy of Serratiopeptidase.

Sample No.	Spike Level	Amount added(mg)	Amount found(mg)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
1	50 %	10	9.8	98%	100%
		10	10.2	102%	
		10	10	100%	
2	100 %	20	19.8	99%	100%
		20	20.2	101%	
		20	20	100%	
3	150 %	30	29.6	98.66%	99.33%
		30	30	100%	
		30	29.8	99.33%	

ROBUSTNESS:**Effect of variation in Flow rate****Table.No: 26. Robustness results for Lornoxicam (flow rate)**

S.No	Drug	Flow Rate ml/min		
		0.8 ml/min R _t	1 ml/min R _t	1.2m l/min R _t
1	Lornoxicam Robustness Results	3.498	3.568	3.125
USP Plate count		2511	2490	2484
USP Tailing		1.65	1.62	1.67

Table.No: 27. Robustness results for Paracetamol (flow rate):

S.No	Drug	Flow Rate ml/min		
		0.8ml/min R _t	1ml/min R _t	1.2m l/min R _t
1	Paracetamol Robustness Results	4.418	4.480	4.175
USP Plate count		2279	2232	2185
USP Tailing		1.47	1.49	1.51

Table.No: 28. Robustness results for Serratiopeptidase (flow rate):

S.No	Drug	Flow Rate ml/min		
		0.8ml/min R _t	1ml/min R _t	1.2 m l/min R _t
1	Serratiopeptidase Robustness Results	8.088	8.097	8.254
USP Plate count		2346	2556	2096
USP Tailing		1.28	1.24	1.27

Effect of variation of mobile phase composition:

Table.No: 29. Robustness results for Lornoxicam:

S.No	Drug	Mobile phase		
		More organic R_t	Organic R_t	Less organic R_t
1	Lornoxicam Robustness Results	3.127	3.568	3.126
JSP Plate count		2510	2490	2492
USP Tailing		1.54	1.62	1.63

Table.No: 30. Robustness results for Paracetamol:

S.No	Drug	Mobile phase		
		More organic R_t	Organic R_t	Less organic R_t
1	Paracetamol Robustness Results	4.177	4.480	4.176
JSP Plate count		2432	2262	2223
USP Tailing		1.35	1.48	1.50

Table.No:31: Robustness results for Serratiopeptidase:

S.No	Drug	Mobile phase		
		More organic R_t	Organic R_t	Less organic R_t
1	Serratiopeptidase Robustness Results	8.256	8.097	8.255
JSP Plate count		2482	2556	2030
USP Tailing		1.20	1.24	1.31

LIMIT OF DETECTION:**Table.No:32. Results of LOD**

Drug name	Standard deviation(σ)	Slope(s)	LOD(μg)
Lornoxicam	371877.10	3736931	0.33
Paracetamol	431401.80	4068452	0.35
Serratiopeptidase	287058.48	2968429	0.31

LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION:**Table.No:33. Results of LOQ**

Drug name	Standard deviation(σ)	Slope(s)	LOQ(μg)
Lornoxicam	407058.1	4350253	0.94
Paracetamol	501401.8	5502817	0.90
Serratiopeptidase	571877.1	5905125	0.97

Forced degradation studies

Forced degradation of Test sample was performed under acidic, alkaline, heat, photolytic and oxidative stress conditions.

Acid hydrolysis

Forced degradation in acidic media was performed by adding 2 mL 0.1 M HCl to 10 mL of stock solution and the mixture is heated at 60°C for approximately 26hrs and the solution is neutralized by addition of 0.1 M NaOH. The prepared solution is injected and chromatograms were recorded.

Alkaline hydrolysis

Forced degradation in basic media was performed by adding 2 mL 0.1 M NaOH to 10 mL of stock solution and the mixture is heated at 60°C for approximately

26hrs and the solution is neutralized by addition of 0.1 M HCl. The prepared solution is injected and chromatograms were recorded.

Oxidative Degradation

To study the effect of oxidizing conditions, an aliquot of stock solution was added to 1 mL 30 % H₂O₂ solution. The prepared solution 10 μ l is injected and chromatograms were recorded.

Thermal Degradation

To study the effect of temperature an aliquot of stock solution was kept at 70°C for 26 hrs. 10 μ l of resulting solution was injected into HPLC and chromatograms were recorded.

Photolysis

To study the effect of photolysis, an aliquot of stock solution was exposed to UV light for 4hrs

Summary on degradation studies
Results of Stress degradation studies

Stress Condition	Sample-1 (Lornoxicam)			Sample-2 (Paracetamol)			Sample-3(Serratiopeptidase)		
	Area	% Assay	% Degradation	Area	% Assay	% Degradation	Area	% Assay	% Degradation
Acidic	1146950	91.7	8.7	861702	92.4	8.3	850511	91.2	9.6
Alkaline	1150702	92.0	9.8	864501	92.7	8.9	855174	91.7	10.1
Photolytic	1194479	95.5	5.7	881286	94.5	5.9	875654	94.1	6.5
Thermal	1154454	92.3	6.5	867298	93.0	7.6	866365	92.9	8.7
Oxidative	1129439	90.3	11.2	847713	90.9	11.4	843983	90.5	10.9

CONCLUSION:

For routine analytical purpose it is desirable to establish methods capable of analyzing huge number of samples in a short time period with good robustness, accuracy and precision without any prior separation step. HPLC method generates large amount of quality data, which serve as highly powerful and convenient analytical tool.

Lornoxicam & Paracetamol was freely soluble in water and alcohol. Serratiopeptidase was freely soluble in alcohol and sparingly soluble in water. Methanol and potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate (pH 3) was chosen as the mobile phase. The run time of the HPLC procedure was 10 minutes.

The method was validated for system suitability, linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity, ruggedness robustness, LOD and LOQ. The system suitability parameters were within limit, hence it was concluded that the system was suitable to perform the assay. The method shows linearity between the concentration range of 10-100 µg / ml. The % recovery of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase were found to be in the range of 99.22 % - 100.11 %. As there was no interference due to excipients and mobile phase, the method was found to be specific. The method was robust and rugged as observed from insignificant variation in the results of analysis by changes in Flow rate and

Mobile phase composition separately and analysis being performed by different analysts.

Good agreement was seen in the assay results of Pharmaceutical formulation by developed method. Hence it can be concluded that the proposed method was a good approach for obtaining reliable results and found to be suitable for the routine analysis of Lornoxicam, Paracetamol and Serratiopeptidase in Pharmaceutical formulation .

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